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EFFECTIVENESS OF RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS AT MILLTEC MACHINERY PVT LTD

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Abstract

The study on “Effectiveness of Recruitment and Selection Process” carried out at Milltec Machinery Private Ltd Company. This company is located in Bommasandra, Bangalore. The main purpose of the study is to hunt, how the Recruitment and Selection in the organisation are carried out and the various techniques used to recruit applicants. Further the objective of my study is to find out the strategies used by the organisation in recruitment and selection process and its effectiveness. And the outcome of my study is to provide necessary suggestions where there is a scope for improvement in order to make the process more effective. This study is carried out by gathering necessary information from various departments. It will also help us to know the employees attitudes are towards the current system and policies used to recruit applicants in all the departments. From the study, the findings determine that the organisation is doing timeliness recruitment and selection process and manpower planning is efficient. It is also found that the organisation uses external source as its main source of recruitment and it is effectiveness.

Key Words: Recruitment, Selection, employee attitudes

INTRODUCTION

Recruitment and Selection plays an important role where it acts as a basement to build Organisation’s efficiency by attracting effective and prospective candidates who can fulfil the goals of the Organisation and help in increasing its growth in the society. Recruiting and Selecting highly skilled candidates are the main objective of all the Organisations in the society. Recruitment is a process of hiring prospective candidates who are capable of filling the job position that can enhance Organisation’s future growth and results in better way. Recruiting effective candidates is the main goal and objective for any Organisation. Hence the methods and strategies adopted in this process should be as effective in order to reach the goals of the Organisation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tuluan, Mayra Madria(2014) studied “Perceived effectiveness of Recruitment and Selection process for Uniformed Personnel of the Philippine National Police” and revealed that organisations give more preference to hard technical skills instead considering their soft behavioural skills which helps in understanding that the employees can be quickly trained and their potential traits. Based on the paper “The Recruitment and Selection Process of Pharmaceutical Companies in Bangladesh: A Case on GlaxoSmithKline Bangladesh Limited”, says that while recruiting the candidates it is necessary to identify the prospective candidate who can contribute to fulfil the strategic aim of the organisation. According to Elhusein H. Elaser, in the paper “The Effectiveness of Selected Human Resources Management Practices on Organisational Performance and Objectives (A Case Study of the Libyan Iron and Steel Company)” it is studied that the recruiting methods should contain more situational rounds such as facing risks, overcoming stress, aptitude tests should be adopted in order to make recruitment more effective. As suggested in the paper “Literature Review: Graduate Recruitment and Selection”, the effective recruitment and selection process enables the organisation to avoid undesirable costs such as employee turnover costs, customers

dissatisfaction, and poor performance of the employees. This strategy also provides mutual benefit to the organization and employees in employment relationship (Raybould, and Sheedy, 2005).

According to NandiniSudheer, in his paper“Effectiveness of Recruitment and Selection at L & T InfoTech” the method of finding effectiveness in recruitment and selection process is to view the opinions and views of new joiners and giving main importance to their work experience. According to the article “Recruitment and Selection Practices and Customer Service Delivery among Selected Banks in Ekiti State, Nigeria” the purpose of recruitment and section process is to meet the requirement of the job, hence the selected candidate should possess the needed personality traits like openness to experience, emotional stability, self-efficacy, since all these characteristics in the candidate leads to be effective and efficiency at work (OladeleOlajide Patrick, 2013).

Based on the paper “Recruitment and Selection Practices in Manufacturing SMEs in Japan”, effective recruitment and selection process can help organisation increase its efficiency, labour productivity, financial performance, and growth. Hence it is important to make effective strategies by human resources in recruitment process (Aruna S, 2015). According to the paper “Recruitment and Selection in Public Organizations In Nigeria: A Case Study of University of Nigeria, Nsukka” it is described that in order to manage resources, money, men, and work and to maintain organisation, suitably qualified people should be recruited in both non managerial and managerial functions (Ifedimmafeoma, 2011). As per the paper “Recruitment and Selection in China: an application to the case of Lenovo” it is recommended that it is better to use the own company website ad provide company application to candidates for different categories. In this case the organisation can easily direct the candidates who can meet minimum requirements (Hui’an CHEN, 2006).

Based on the study of “An Empirical Analysis of Recruitment and Selection Practices in the Public Sector” says that when the vacancy is identified, the first step is to determine job analysis clearly and effectively so that the organisation will be clear where the job responsibilities fit in organisation and leads to recruiting of candidates of suitable qualification and skills. This ensures effective process of selecting candidates for organisation (Evans BrakoNtiamoah, 2010).

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the strategies in recruitment and selection process followed in the Organisation.
- 2) To analyse and understand the effectiveness of recruitment process and identify various areas where there can be scope for improvement.
- 3) To suggest and provide a systematic recruitment process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Present research is descriptive in nature and Probability Sampling technique has been used and sample is 100. The sampling elements considered here are the employees of the organisation under study. Data collection has been done using two sources. One, Primary data was collected through Questionnaire in which series of questions provided in a sheet regarding research is narrated and distributed to the respondents. The contents are linked to research in order to gather information about study. Second method of data collection is data collected from secondary sources like company websites, Company documents. Journals, Books and Internet search has been used to study in-depth about the subject.

ANALYSIS

The data thus collected is analysed to arrive at findings and to propose suggestions

Table 1 – Responses of the sample

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1.The organization is doing timeliness recruitment and Selection process	22	70	8	0	0	100
2.HR provide an adequate pool of quality applicants	68	29	3	0	0	100
3.4.HR team acts as a consultant to enhance the quality of the applicant pre-screening process?	52	31	17	0	0	100
5.Internal hiring helps in motivating the employees	79	19	1	1	0	100
6.Job hiring via e-recruitment gives competitive advantage over other organisations	26	66	8	0	0	100
7.External recruiting brings out more desirable employees than the internal recruiting.	26	58	6	10	0	100
8.All the processes related to Recruitment are maintained in a single department of the organization.	42	37	8	11	2	100
9. Manpower planning is efficiently working in identifying the vacant positions	63	22	9	4	2	100

GRAPH– Responses of the sample in percentage

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The above table and graph indicates that 70% of the respondents “agree” that organization do timeliness recruitment & selection process, 22% of the candidates “strongly agree” that the organisation is doing timeliness recruitment & selection process and the 8% of the respondents are “Undecided” about the timeliness recruitment and selection process in the organisation.68% of the respondents “strongly agree” that HR provides an adequate pool of quality applicants, 29% “agree” that HR provides an adequate pool of quality applicants, and 3% of the respondents are “Undecided” that HR provides an adequate pool of quality applicants. 68% of the respondents “strongly Agree” that the HR team acts as consultant in pre-screening process, 29% of the respondents “agree” that the HR team acts as consultant in pre-screening process, and 3% of the respondents “Undecided” that the HR team acts as consultant in pre-screening process.79% of the respondents “strongly agree” that internal hiring helps in motivating the employees, 19% of respondents “agree”, 1% of respondents are “Undecided”, and 1% of respondents “Disagree” that internal hiring helps in motivating the employees.

66% of the respondents “agree” that the job hiring via e-recruitment gives competitive advantage in selecting applicants 26% of the respondents “strongly agree” that the job hiring via e-recruitment gives competitive advantage in selecting applicant and 8% of the respondents are “undecided” that the job hiring via e-recruitment gives competitive advantage in selecting applicant organisations.58% of the respondents “agree” that external recruiting brings out more desirable employees than the internal recruiting, 25% of the respondents “strongly agree”,10% of the respondents say they “disagree”, and 7% of the respondents are “undecided” that external recruiting brings out more desirable employees than the internal recruiting.

42% of the respondents “strongly agree” that processes related to recruitment are maintained in a single department of the organization, 37% of the respondents “agree”, 11% of the respondents “disagree,” 8% of the respondents are “Undecided”, 11% of the respondents “disagree”, and 2% of the respondents “Strongly Disagree” that the processes related to recruitment are maintained in a single department of the organization.63% of the respondents “strongly agree” manpower planning is efficient in the organisation,22% of the respondents “agree” that manpower planning is efficient in the organisation,9% of the respondents “disagree” manpower planning is efficient in the organisation 4% of the respondents are “undecided” and 2% of the respondents “strongly disagree” that the manpower planning is efficient in the organisation.

As said by the employees the organisation is doing timeliness recruitment and selection process, 22% of the employees strongly agree about this and 70% of them agree, and 8% of the employees are not aware of this and are undecided. Hence the recruitment and selection process should be made aware to all the employee and process should be done at proper time and place.Most of the employees say that they agree that job hiring via e-recruitment gives competitive advantage over other organisations and only less employees strongly agree to that and few are undecided about this. Hence make aware of the employees about the effective recruiting sources.

External recruiting brings out a lot of fascinating staff than the internal recruiting; this can be powerfully united and most agreed by fewer employees and agreed by more employees. We strongly recommend that the internal sources also should be considered for recruiting.External sources such as LinkedIn, and Facebook, can be used since now a days, many people are active in social media who are in search of job and will also be able to get high number of candidates to apply for job. This source helps in bringing high quantity of candidates and also to hire best quality applicants as it is recommended.Practical implementation for engineering students such as product testing and product handling which ensures safety handling of machinery and tools and also human safety.Design engineering should be conducted designing of tools and machines that are to be taken for the R & D department. Quality assurance testing tools should be used to test the trial design for candidates.Process adherence and safety knowledge test should be adopted in order to ensure that the candidate is aware of safety measurement and knowledge about the process of machines as well as workersSituational awareness testes should be taken that

ensures the workers ability to face with the situations in the environment they work with and the safety and awareness.

CONCLUSION

From this research study, it can be concluded that the organisation is doing timeliness recruitment and selection process and provide adequate pool of quality applicants. The study also says that internal recruitment helps in motivating the employees as strongly agreed by most of the respondents. Hence internal hiring that includes employee referrals should be considered, since this can ensure employee retention by motivating the employees in hiring internally. External sources such as LinkedIn, and Facebook, can be used since now a days many people are active in social media who are in search of job and will also be able to get high number of candidates to apply for job. This source helps in bringing high quantity of candidates and also to hire best quality applicants as it is recommended. From the suggestions it is considered that the efficiency can be reached by adopting required tests and the use of effective sources in recruiting.

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